

Analysis of the XE Prime Experimental Reactor at Dry Conditions

Camden Eck^{1,*}, Dan Kotlyar¹

¹Nuclear and Radiological Engineering and Medical Physics Program, George W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA, 30332-0405 USA

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) is an experimental rocket engine concept in which hydrogen propellant is heated by a reactor. While there are modern efforts to build such systems, the primary sources of test data continue to be historic designs built and operated in the 1960s and 1970s as part of the NERVA program. Thus, benchmarks of these designs are vital for evaluating and comparing the performance of new codes and methods of analysis. This work provides fully documented and reproducible models for the XE Prime Experimental reactor. Validation benchmarks of the drum worth curves under the dry condition are presented. Additional benchmarks are shown for an alternative arrangement in which TaC loading is removed from certain elements. Discrepancies between modeled results and reference data are within or nearly within error margins for all drum angles and reactivity worths measured.

Keywords: XE Prime, nuclear thermal propulsion, benchmark, validation, verification

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nuclear Engine for Rocket Vehicle Application (NERVA) program, which began in 1961, focused on developing a Nuclear Thermal Propulsion (NTP) rocket engine. NTP engines utilize a fission reactor as a heat exchanger for liquid hydrogen propellant [1]. Until the program's termination in 1973, it produced a lineage of experimental reactors and engines, culminating in XE Prime, a complete engine system containing all major subcomponents in flight configuration. In a ground test, the system achieved a power output of 1,140 MW for 210 seconds [2]. Figure 1 presents the schematics of the XE Prime core and assembly.

Figure 1. XE Prime reactor trimetric view (left) and core assembly view (right).

*ceck3@gatech.edu

Because its design was so matured, and because there is a wealth of available data, the XE Prime system is a useful case study for bolstering modern day analysis methods used for NTP. Like modern designs, the XE Prime active core was composed of long fuel elements with orificed channels for hydrogen coolant flow. Additionally, it utilized beryllium reflectors with rotating control drums containing boron-based neutron poisoning material. These rotating control drums, along with the mass flow rate of the hydrogen coolant, comprised the main control mechanisms of the engine. Some of these characteristics are substantially different from modern designs. Namely, the fuel pellets contained highly enriched uranium. Thus, the core achieved criticality with considerably less moderating power, resulting in a relatively small amount of moderating material relative to the full volume of the active core [3].

The reference model developed in this study will help generate reference solutions and validation benchmarks, which will, in turn, help validate other high-fidelity stochastic and deterministic analyses. They will also be useful in analyses which seek to model thermal hydraulics and couple thermal feedback effects, which will be the focus of future work. This paper focuses on the dry, zero-power operating condition.

2. METHODOLOGY

This section details the simulation environment and presents verification analyses that ensures alignment between the reported reactor setup and the computational model

2.1. Computational Environment

All calculations for all validation exercises were performed with the Monte Carlo, Serpent 2.2.1, code using coupled neutron-photon transport [4, 5]. Cross sections were generated using the ENDF/B-VII.1 library [6]. The Monte Carlo statistical uncertainty for all eigenvalue calculations is under 6.0 pcm. All calculations ran 500,000 particle histories for 100 inactive and 500 active cycles. Modeled uncertainties are purely the statistical uncertainty of the Monte Carlo neutron transport solutions. They do not include cross-section uncertainties or uncertainties arising because of simplifications or inconsistencies within the model.

Uncertainty reporting in XE Prime documentation is unavailable for some measures. For measures where it is available, the details and causes are often not fully delineated. Where possible, reference uncertainties have been included.

2.2. Model Construction

This section details the model definition, including its geometry, dimensions, and material densities. To replicate the dry, zero-power condition, all solids are held to room temperature (300 K), and all coolant regions are represented as void.

2.2.1. Active Core

The active core is composed of various types of hexagonal elements. These fall within two main categories, fueled and unfueled, which are most commonly arranged into “regular cluster” configurations. This configuration features an unfueled element bordered on all six sides by fueled elements.

There are a total of 1584 fuel elements in the core. Each fuel element is made of a graphite matrix which has been loaded with fuel pellets made of UC with 93.15% enrichment and which has been orificed to contain 19, equally spaced flow channels. Additionally, each matrix is coated with NbC on both its outer edges and its interior channel walls. All the fueled matrices have a length at the end which is not loaded with any fuel. This is referred to as the “unfueled tip.” There are many characteristics which differentiate the fuel elements from each other. These include seven classifications for the amount of UC loaded into the graphite matrix, loading differences within each classification depending on each

element's supplier, unfueled tip length, orifice diameter, and NbC coating thickness [3]. As the reported values result in a cumbersome number of permutations for possible element definitions, some simplifying steps were necessary:

- Unfueled tip length is set to one inch for all elements. This was appropriate because most elements have the one-inch unfueled tip.
- NbC coating is set to 1.64 mils for all elements. This is the average coating thickness given.
- Uncoated orifice diameter is set to 98.28 mils for all elements. This is the given average channel diameter (95 mils) plus the given average NbC coating thickness.
- A consistent fuel loading is assigned to each loading code, calculated from as-built data.

Thus, the model produced in serpent only has seven different kinds of fuel elements, one for each loading code. For the code "99", a weighted average was calculated based on the number of Y-12-supplied vs. WAFF-supplied elements. Figure 2 shows a representative Serpent model of a single fuel element.

Figure 2: Fueled element top-down view (left) and side view (right). Marked dimensions are in cm.

There are 289 unfueled elements in the XE Prime core. All unfueled elements are composed primarily of graphite matrix material without any UC pellets loaded into it, the same composition as the fuel elements' unfueled tip segment. A single, large hole is orificed into the graphite matrix, within which sits a thick insulation layer of pyrolytic graphite. Within the insulation layer is thin liner of stainless steel surrounding a hydrogen coolant channel. This coolant channel is annular, with a solid tie rod in the middle made of Inconel-718. There are two thin hydrogen gaps, one between the stainless-steel liner and the insulation, and another between the insulation and the graphite matrix. Similar to the fuel elements, the graphite matrix of the unfueled elements has been coated with NbC. This coating, however, is not well defined in the documentation [3], and it is not included in the Serpent model.

The unfueled elements fall into two main categories, regular and shimmed. The graphite matrix in the regular unfueled elements is exactly the same as the unfueled tip material. For the shimmed unfueled elements, however, the graphite matrix is loaded with TaC. The density of both the unshimmed and shimmed graphite matrix material is given as a specification. For many unshimmed elements, there are also orifices for the insertion of measurement instruments such as thermocouples, thermal capsules, and pressure probes. Elements can have anywhere from zero to four of these orifices. While the size of these instrumentation holes is well defined, their position within the plane of the unfueled element is not [3]. For each instrumented element, instrumentation holes are modeled as midway between the

outer edge of the primary orifice (which contains the insulation and tie rod) and the apothem. The composition of the inserted instrumentation itself is not modeled. Figure 3 shows a representative model of an unfueled element.

Figure 3: Unfueled element top-down view (left) and side view (right). Marked dimensions are in cm.

Figure 4: Model active core configuration (left) with zoomed in view of loading code distribution (bottom-right) compared to reference distribution (top-right) [3]. Blue unfueled elements are standard, and green unfueled elements have been shimmed with TaC.

Three subregions comprise the active core. The central subregion, which is the largest, contains 199 regular clusters. Surrounding the central subregion is the peripheral subregion, which contains 42 irregular clusters arranged into seven different varieties. Between the peripheral subregions and the reflectors is the partial element subregion, consisting of partial, unrefueled hexagons, which are made of the unfueled graphite matrix. The arrangement of regular and irregular clusters, the distribution of fueled elements with regards to loading codes, and the distribution of shimming in the unfueled elements are all rotationally symmetric by 60 degrees. As these distributions are well-documented [3], they have been faithfully reproduced in the Serpent model and are shown in Figure 4.

2.2.2. Reflectors

Surrounding the active core are three main reflector regions. The innermost region is the graphite reflector. This reflector contains 144 equally spaced coolant channels. The second region is the outer reflector, composed of a mixture of Be and Al. Contained within the outer reflector region are 384 coolant channels distributed over four rows, 36 tie bolt channels near the outer edge, and 12 large holes into which the control drum assemblies are placed. Finally, the 12 control drum assemblies are each housed within the outer beryllium reflector at 30-degree intervals. Each drum has 19 coolant channels, a large slot containing a poison vane, and a smaller slot opposing the poison vane. The vane is made of a mixture of B and Al. The full drum is meant to rotate, with the 0-degree position referring to the center of the vane pointing directly to the center of the active core, and the 180-degree position referring to the center of the poison pointing directly away from the core. All drums rotate in the counterclockwise direction over a span of 15 to 165 degrees. Coolant flows through all channels, the small slot, the gaps left by the vane in the large slot space, and the annular space between the outer edge of the drum assembly and the large hole in the outer beryllium reflector. Beyond the reflectors is the pressure vessel [3]. Figure 5 shows the arrangement of the reflectors.

Figure 5: Reflectors top-down view, 30-degree slice.

2.2.3. Shielding and Plena

The model also includes several shielding, plena, and other regions. The first of these is the support block, shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. The support block for each cluster is structurally similar to its corresponding unfueled tip region. Thus, the support block is modeled by extending the entire unfueled tip region of the active core downward by 5.715 cm. A similar approach was taken for the nuclear analysis performed in the documentation.³ For all other regions in this section, their interior gaps, subcomponents, and other complexities were not captured in any available documentation. Thus, each region is assumed to be homogenous in terms of density. Densities were calculated by dividing each region's given mass by its given volume [3]. Figure 6 displays a halved side view of the Serpent model.

Figure 6. Reactor side view with plena and other regions shown. Marked dimensions are in cm.

3. RESULTS

This section details results dealing with the dry-critical drum angle, kinetic parameters, and the reactivity worth of the TaC shims. These characteristics are the most well documented aspects of the XE Prime reactor for the dry condition.

3.1. Criticality Configuration

To find the drum angle at which the reactor is critical while dry, tests were run at seven drum angles ranging from 15 to 165 degrees. This range was chosen to align with the minimum and maximum mechanically allowable drum positions given in the documentation. The five angles between (50, 70, 89, 115, and 130 degrees) were chosen to achieve a reasonable fit within the range of angles at which the model was expected to become critical. Once all the tests were run, a 5th degree polynomial line of best fit was generated for reactivity across the full span. This resulted in a dry-critical drum angle value of 84.69 degrees, compared to a reported reference dry-critical value of 89 degrees. This is well within the 10-degree error margin given by the reference. The drum span found for the model was also relatively close to the reference value, though not quite within its given error range. For the kinetic parameters, the values shown are from the 89-degree run, which was the closest to the calculated dry-critical angle. These generally align well with the reference, particularly the prompt neutron lifetime and the effective delayed neutron fraction. For the precursor groups, the first four groups saw reasonably good alignment for their respective delayed neutron fractions and decay constants, but the fifth and sixth groups, however, saw much larger error. Table I displays all results discussed above. Figure 7 shows the angle-dependent control drum compared to the reference. Note that this is the total bank worth for all twelve drums.

Table I. Critical drum angle and kinetic parameters. Values are reported with $\pm 3\sigma$.

Parameter [units]	Reference Value ³	Modeled Value	Error [%]
Critical drum angle [degrees]	89 ± 10	84.69 ± 0.33	-4.84
Drum span [pcm]	5623 ± 142	6018 ± 23	7.02
Prompt neutron lifetime [sec]	2.4E-05	$2.40007\text{E-}05 \pm 3.5\text{E-}08$	0.00292
β_{eff}	7.1E-03	$7.2607\text{E-}03 \pm 2.5\text{E-}08$	2.35

β_1	2.343E-04	$2.596E-04 \pm 5.0E-06$	10.8
β_2	1.555E-03	$1.320E-03 \pm 1.1E-05$	-15.1
β_3	1.392E-03	$1.264E-03 \pm 1.1E-07$	-9.17
β_4	2.805E-03	$2.788E-03 \pm 1.7E-05$	-0.600
β_5	8.165E-04	1.156E-03 \pm 1.0E-05	41.6
β_6	2.982E-04	4.800E-04 \pm 6.7E-06	61.0
λ_1 [sec ⁻¹]	0.0124	$0.0133 \pm 2.2E-07$	7.55
λ_2 [sec ⁻¹]	0.0305	$0.0327 \pm 4.3E-07$	7.34
λ_3 [sec ⁻¹]	0.111	$0.121 \pm 8.7E-07$	8.81
λ_4 [sec ⁻¹]	0.301	$0.303 \pm 5.4E-06$	0.604
λ_5 [sec ⁻¹]	1.14	0.850 \pm 2.5E-05	-25.5
λ_6 [sec ⁻¹]	3.01	$2.85 \pm 1.7E-04$	-5.197

Figure 7. Control drum bank worth.

3.2. Shimmed reactivity worth

The next set of tests analyzed the reactivity worth of the shims in the 24 unfueled elements that were loaded with TaC. To perform this test, the Serpent model was run again. In this new set of tests, the 24 TaC elements were replaced with regular unfueled elements. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the unshimmed model. Note that it is identical except for the lack of shimmed, unfueled elements.

The unshimmed model was run at four drum angle positions over the same span (15 to 165 degrees). The other two angles chosen (64 and 74 degrees) were again used to straddle the expected dry-critical drum angle of the model. Once reactivity values were obtained for each run, a 3rd degree polynomial fit was used, similarly to the previous set of tests, to predict the dry-critical drum angle. This resulted in an angle of 69.27 degrees, compared to the reference value of 74 degrees. Once again, this is well within the reference error.

The reactivity difference is the excess reactivity of the unshimmed model relative to the shimmed model. Average reactivity difference was calculated by taking the difference of the unshimmed and shimmed polynomial fits, then integrating the difference over the full drum span. This resulted in a calculated reactivity difference of 814.5 pcm compared to the 766.8 pcm given by the reference. Once again, this is well within the reference error margin. Table II shows detailed results.

Table III. Unshimmed model results.

Parameter [units]	Reference Value	Modeled Value	Error [%]
Critical drum angle [degrees]	74 ± 10	69.27 ± 0.30	-6.39

Reactivity, drums in [pcm]	-2009 ± 540	-1949 ± 19	-2.99
Reactivity, drums out [pcm]	3614 ± 540	3936 ± 14	8.91
Drum span [pcm]	5623 ± 142	5885 ± 23	4.66
Avg. reactivity difference, relative to shimmed reactor [pcm]	766.8 ± 221	814.5 ± 24	6.22

4. CONCLUSIONS

The accessibility of benchmarks for historic NTP systems is crucial for validating modern codes and methods of analysis. Thanks to the extensive, available data characterizing the construction and testing of XE Prime, a comprehensive benchmark of the reactor is feasible. Thus, the models detailed in this paper successfully replicated the reactor's most important dimensions and material compositions, as shown by the verification studies.

In testing these models, they were also shown to successfully reproduce a range of reactor physics behavior reported by the documentation. The best agreement was seen measuring the control drum bank worth curve, where all results were within the reference error except for the 165-degree run, which was only slightly off. Similarly, the unshimmed runs showed excellent agreement, both in terms of dry-critical angle and added reactivity. Much of the discrepancy that does exist for these results can likely be attributed to simplifications in the model definition, particularly with the shielding and plena regions. These regions provide a not insignificant amount of axial reflection to the active core. Modeling them with a higher fidelity would have most likely brought the error down noticeably.

The models discussed in this paper are a first step in developing a set of reproduceable XE Prime benchmarks. Future work will focus on strengthening this benchmark by defining and validating the cold and hot operating conditions. The models, calculations, and results are all contained in the <https://github.gatech.edu/dkotlyar6/XE-PrimeGitHub> repository accessible through the Georgia Institute of Technology and will be made available upon request.

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